

Unveiling Openness in Energy Research: A Bibliometric Analysis Focusing on Open Access and Data Sharing Practices

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Introduction

Open science practices are essential for advancing energy research, particularly fostering transparency, collaboration, and reproducibility [1]. This study examines openness in energy research by analyzing trends in open access (OA) publishing and data-sharing practices. The application of bibliometric methods reveals the evolution of OA publications and the utilization of data on a quantitative basis. This yields insights into current practices and the identification of gaps that must be addressed to achieve the objectives of NFDI4Energy [2].

Research Questions

We examine these research questions on OA and data sharing in the field of energy research:

- What percentage of energy research publications are OA? How do the types (gold, green, etc. [3]) of these publications differ?
- Are there notable differences in OA and data sharing practices in different subfields of energy research?
- How commonly are datasets for energy studies shared? What are the primary repositories used?
- What kind of data sharing or publication practices are widespread? How has this evolved over the last decade?

Methods

A bibliometric analysis was conducted using **OpenAlex**¹, an open and comprehensive metadata repository for scholarly outputs. OpenAlex aligns with the principles of open science, ensuring that both the data source and the methodology are openly accessible [4].

The corpus for the bibliometric analyses in this study was collected on December 6th, 2024, using the OpenAlex API. A total of **18,598** articles were identified by API call with the URL (https://api.openalex.org/works?page=1&filter=primary_topic.field.id:fields/21,authorships.institutions.continent:g46.publication_year:2013-2023,authorships.countries:countries/de), using the following criteria: OpenAlex field "Energy", continent "Europe", country "Germany", and publication years 2013 – 2023.

¹ <https://openalex.org/works>

The data corpus was imported into Google Sheets, where a initial comprehensive analysis was conducted.

OA Publishing Trends

We investigated the percentage of OA articles across energy research subfields in comparison to closed access articles, as well as the different types of OA. Furthermore, we analyzed the development over time of OA in comparison to closed access.

Data-Sharing Practices

As datasets are also indexed in OpenAlex, it is possible to assess the prevalence of data-sharing mentions in publications. The most frequently occurring source repositories can therefore be identified.

This analysis has revealed that OpenAlex only categorises datasets as datasets when they are stored and described separately in source repositories. These datasets are partially independent of related papers, but the datasets assigned as supplemental material or integrated as figures or tables in the paper are not indexed as datasets in OpenAlex. This prompts a more in-depth examination of the data corpus and a closer look at the various data-sharing practices observed among the papers in our data corpus. Given the substantial size of the corpus (18,598 papers), a stratified random sampling method [5] was employed, with a targeted sample size of approximately 500 publications from the original data corpus.

A python code was run to implement the stratified sampling process. First, the 18,598 entries were divided into the defined two strata. Then, a proportional number of samples were randomly selected from each stratum. A subsequent analysis of data-sharing practices was conducted on this sample.

Results

OA Publishing

The majority (88%) of the corpus publications pertain to renewable energy research, and nearly half (48%) are OA (see Table 1). This trend can presumably be attributed to robust policy support, including funding agency mandates and OA journal influence. The nuclear energy subfield shows substantial OA adoption (85% of publications); however, the low quantity of publications in this subfield increases the impact of any metadata errors or duplications.

Table 1: OA and Closed Access in Energy Subfields.

Subfield	OA					Closed	Total	% OA
	bronze	diamond	gold	green	hybrid			
Renewable Energy, Sustainability and the Environment	1137	301	2036	2220	2152	8650	16496	48%
Energy Engineering and Power Technology	78	16	190	111	176	741	1312	44%
General Energy	38	19	48	84	32	446	667	33%
Fuel Technology	12	3	15		1	31	62	50%
Nuclear Energy and Engineering	33	3	16			9	61	85%
Total	1298	342	2305	2415	2361	9877	18598	

The selected timeframe (2013 – 2023) permits an evaluation of OA publication evolution, showing considerable scope for improvement. While the number of closed publications remains relatively stable, OA publications have gradually increased, reaching parity with closed publications by mid-2020 and subsequently surpassing closed publications (see Figure 1). Nevertheless, across this ten-year span, OA publications are still somewhat less common than closed publications (see Figure 2).

Closed Publications vs. OA Publications

Figure 1: Closed vs. OA Publications (2013-2023).

Distribution of papers in %

Figure 2: Distribution of Papers.

Data-Sharing Practices

1. Dataset indexed in OpenAlex

280 dataset records were identified from the data corpus, making up only 1.5% of the entire corpus (see Figure 3). Zenodo is a predominant repository, with 192 records. It is notable that the vast majority of these datasets are freely accessible.

Figure 3: Distribution of Work Types.

In comparison to the number of publications within our data corpus, the insufficient number of datasets leads to the conclusion that datasets are not comprehensively indexed in OpenAlex. This finding indicates also that the practice of data publication as a distinct and independent form of publication is not as widespread as open access publication. However, when examining the institutions publishing these datasets, an interesting picture emerges (see Tables 2 and 3).

Table 2: German Institutions with Most Open Datasets. (Entire Corpus)

Rank	Institutions	Datasets
1	Bielefeld University (co-authored with Macquarie University [Australia])	10
2	Centre for European Economic Research	9
3	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e.V. (DLR)	6
4	Brandenburg University of Applied Sciences	6
5 & 6	Friedrich Schiller University Jena; Leibniz Institute of Photonic Technology (co-authors)	5
7	Forschungszentrum Jülich (co-authored with Queen Mary University of London [UK])	4
8	Zuse Institute Berlin	3
9 & 10	University of Giessen; Technische Universität Berlin (co-authors)	3

Table 3: Institutions with Most Publications. (Fractional Authorship Counting) (Entire Corpus)

Rank	Institutions	Publications (frac)
1	Technische Universität Berlin	480,24
2	Technical University of Munich	403,03
3	RWTH Aachen University	393,01
4	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	371,11
5	Ruhr University Bochum	350,33
6	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	324,34
7	Forschungszentrum Jülich	315,69
8	Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt e. V. (DLR)	290,54
9	Technical University of Darmstadt	277,64
10	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie	196,25

Table 4: Institutions with Most Publications. (Full Authorship Counting) (Entire Corpus)

Rank	Institutions	Publications (full)
1	Technische Universität Berlin	1061
2	Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg	852
3	Forschungszentrum Jülich	828
4	Technical University of Munich	814
5	Ruhr University Bochum	773
6	RWTH Aachen University	735
7	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology	684
8	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie	514
9	Technical University of Darmstadt	510
10	Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion	487

Technische Universität Berlin publishes most prominently, with both fractional and full counting of authorship (Table 3 and Table 4), yet it lags in data sharing. Only two other top-publishing institutions are included in Table 2 as institutions with datasets (highlighted in bold font in the tables). However, the remainder of the institutions with many publications are not in Table 2.

Additionally, a notable divergence exists between the amount of published data (Table 3) and accessible data (Table 2). Despite the promotion of data sharing in numerous initiatives, implementation by researchers remains inadequate. This in-between result prompts further investigation into the data.

2. Dataset not indexed in OpenAlex

With a systematic sampling method, stratified random sampling, a sample with of approximately 500 publications from the original data corpus was extracted.

The following tables present the defined stratification criteria and proportionally allocated sample numbers in each stratum, thus facilitating the attainment of a representative sample that reflects the key characteristics of the corpus.

Table 5: Sample Allocation by Subfield.

Subfield	Nr. of works	% in Corpus	Expected in Sample
Renewable Energy, Sustainability and the Environment	16496	88,70%	443
Energy Engineering and Power Technology	1312	7,05%	35
General Energy	667	3,59%	18
Fuel Technology	62	0,33%	2
Nuclear Energy and Engineering	61	0,33%	2
Total	18598		500

Table 6: Sample Allocation by Publication Year.

Year Range	% in Corpus	Expected in Sample (500)
2013-2016	29%	144
2017-2020	37%	184
2021-2023	34%	171

In the sample by subfield (Table 5) of 500 works, 492 are assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), while 8 do not possess one. For a more comprehensive analysis, it is necessary to obtain the full texts of these works. For the 492 works with DOIs, a full-text search is carried out within the Dimension² database. This database contains 466 works from this search and provides additional information about the works.

Figure 4: Number of Publications sorted by Fields of Research (ANZSRC 2020) in Dimensions.

² <https://app.dimensions.ai/discover/publication>

Since "Energy" is not an independent research category in the Dimension database, the publications in this sample range across different research categories, as shown in Figure 4. The categories listed here demonstrate the interdisciplinary nature of energy research. However, by selecting the classification "Sustainable Development Goals", the relevance of the content of the publications to the energy sector was identified. This also provided an initial overview to the quality of the corpus.

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Figure 5: Number of Publications sorted by Sustainable Development Goals in Dimensions

An examination of the publication status within the research institution reveals that the top 10 institutions are presented in Table 7. Compared to Table 4, which is based on the original data corpus, there is an 80% overlap, thereby reflecting the representativeness of the sample.

Table 7: Institutions with Most Publications (Corpus Sample).

Rank	Name	Publications (full)
1	Technical University of Berlin (TUB)	33
2	University of Erlangen-Nuremberg (FAU)	29
3	Ruhr University Bochum (RUB)	26
4	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)	21
5	Forschungszentrum Jülich (FZJ)	20
6	Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion	17
7	TU Dresden (TUD)	16
8	Technical University of Munich (TUM)	15
9	German Aerospace Center (DLR)	15
10	RWTH Aachen University (RWTH)	13

In order to identify datasets integrated directly into the publication, a keyword search was conducted using combinations such as ("**Data availability***") OR ("**Supplementary material***") OR ("**Raw data availability***") OR ("**code availability***") OR ("**Dataset available at***") OR ("**Experimental data***") OR ("**Data and materials availability***"). This search was designed to identify particular statement sections such as "data availability statement" or "supplementary material statement", as well as datasets that are only integrated into full-text papers. The keyword search yielded 135 results out of 466 papers, indicating that approximately 24% of the papers have datasets mentioned. The institutions related to these 135 papers are ranked in Table 8.

Table 8: German Institutions with Most Datasets (Corpus Sample).

Rank	Institutions	Publications with integrated datasets
1	University of Erlangen-Nuremberg (FAU)	9
2	Technical University of Berlin (TUB)	8
3	Max Planck Institute for Chemical Energy Conversion	7
4	Ruhr University Bochum (RUB)	7
5	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)	7
6	TU Dresden (TUD)	6
7	Technical University of Munich (TUM)	6
8	Freie Universität Berlin (FU)	5
9	University of Duisburg-Essen	5
10	RWTH Aachen University (RWTH)	5

When compared with the publication status of the sample (see Table 7), the ranks following this analysis appear more logical and reasonable.

The aforementioned analysis was executed on the sample according to the publication years (see Table 5). For this sample, 490 were assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), while 10 lacked one. A DOI search in Dimensions yielded 475 matching publications. The keyword search with ("**Data availability***") OR ("**Supplementary material***") OR ("**Raw data availability***") OR ("**code availability***") OR ("**Dataset available at***") OR ("**Experimental data***") OR ("**Data and materials availability***") yielded 110 results out of 475 papers, that meant around 23% of the publications mentioned data integration or supplemented with data. This result is almost the same as the result based on the sample by subfield.

This sample analysis indicates that the amount or proportion of data publication is significantly higher than the 1.5% of paper publication indicated by the initial results from the Open-Alex dataset indexing. Furthermore, data integration and supplementation are mentioned in more than 20% of paper publications.

The development of data sharing from 2013 to 2023 is illustrated in the figure 5, which demonstrates a slight upward trend overall, though it also exhibits declines during the 2019 interval. Notably, the decline in the final period (2023) is particularly pronounced, indicating an unfortunate deviation from the positive trend observed in previous periods.

Figure 5: Development of Publications with Data Integration and Supplementation based on the Sample Sets by Subfield.

Conclusion

While bibliometric analysis provides valuable insights, it does have limitations.

1. The methodology relies on quantitative metrics and does not allow for a qualitative analysis of publication content, such as assessing the usability or richness of shared data.
2. The findings depend on the quality and completeness of metadata in OpenAlex as well as Dimensions. Missing, duplicate, or inconsistent metadata can skew results, especially in underrepresented subfields.
3. Publications may share data without reporting it in a way captured by bibliometric tools, leading to potential underestimation of this practice.

Despite this, the study provides a valuable baseline for understanding openness in energy research. The results highlight opportunities for improvement, particularly in encouraging more OA adoption and data sharing. This study underscores OA variability across energy research subfields and highlights gaps in OA publishing and data-sharing practices. Notably, the practice of independent data publication in repositories with comprehensive metadata is not yet widely adopted in this research community, although data integration and supplementation in publications is marginally more prevalent. These findings underscore the imperative for standardising data publication practices, particularly the independent and separate publication of datasets. This approach could potentially ensure greater visibility and availability of datasets than merely integrating or supplementing data directly within the publication itself.

While bibliometric analysis provides a useful starting point, further research is needed to address the quality and reusability of shared data, as well as the network of institutional collaborations producing this data.

Author contributions

Linna Lu contributed in conceptualization, methodology, writing - original draft.
Amanda Wein contributed in conceptualization, methodology, writing – review & editing.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Data Availability

Data generated or analysed within this study are partially included in this Abstract as Tables and Figures. The entire data corpus and the sample corpus as Dataset published separately also on Zenodo and located here:

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